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Review Paper

Review on: Oral dissolving film: An Emerging Platform for Rapid Drug Delivery

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ABSTRACT

In the recent year many of pharmaceutical groups are focusing their research on rapid dissolving technology. This technology has been used for local action, rapid release product. This technology has evolved over the past few years from the confection of breath strip and become a novel and widely accepted form by consumer. Oral fast dissolving film is the type of drug delivery system which when placed in oral cavity disintegrate or dissolve of few second without the intake of water. These film have potentially deliver the drug systematically through intragastric sublingual or buccal route of administration and also has been used local action. These film have been alternative for the solid dosage form and liquid dosage form like capsule, Tablet, syrup. These film dissolve quickly when they come in contact with a tongue without need of extra liquid and without chewing. First developed fast dissolving dosage form in formulation and the rapid disintegration properties, we obtained through special formulation modification, hence mouth dissolving film is proved to better alternative in such case. This fast dissolving drug delivery system is bypass the first pass metabolism. Oral film of the new days having one of the highest patient compliance safety and are economical than most other dosage form. Hydrophilic polymer are used to create a film that quickly dissolve in the tongue, fast dissolving oral film are helpful to paediatric and geriatric patient who experience difficulties in swallowing traditional oral solid dosage form. Fast dissolving film provide better drug dissolution, faster onset of action. The oral film are formulated using polymers, plasticiser, flavour, colour and sweeteners. Oral film are use in anti asthmatic, antiallergic, anti ulcer, Anti-epileptic, antitussive and expectorants drugs [

INTRODUCTION

In 1970s fast dissolving drug delivery system were developed as an alternative to traditional drug

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delivery system like syrup, tablet, capsule. Recent technology advancement have diverted many drug company to explore new prospective in this technology to provide fast, accurate dosing that is expected to increase compliance, particularly among Children. This method provide a number of significant advantages over the traditional solid dosage form such as tablet, capsule and syrup. Oral dissolving film is one amongst the new approach to increasing patient acceptance dissolution.[2,14,21]

It is a novel drug system for the oral delivery of drug. This delivery system consist of very thin oral strip. It is used for geriatric and paediatric patient who had difficulty ingestion typical oral solid dosage form. The oral film placed on the patient tongue or oral mucosal tissue, the film hydrate rapidly and adhere on to the location of action. Oral dissolving film which disintegrate or dissolve within second when placed in the mouth without

drinking of water or chewing it dissolve rapidly and release active pharmaceutical ingredients for systemic absorption. Oral mouth dissolving film improve patient compliance fast dissolving film easy to use especially for the patient who have difficult swelling pill such as child elderly. The ability of oral film dissolve quickly on require and the dosage can be administered directly. The film designed to disintegrate within a second upon contact with the environment of the oral cavity provide quicker onset of therapeutic effect. The large surface area of the film expose to the moist oral environment accelerate the disintegration process, Ensuring that the drug is quickly available for absorption, either through [for directly enter to the blood stream]. Oral film avoids swallowing Issue. There's for fast dissolving film have become a popular oral dosage form for various medicaments.[1,12,13]

United state food and drug administration [USFDA] define the fast dissolving film as a thin, flexible, non friable polymeric film strip containing one or more dispersed dissolve active pharmaceutical ingredients. The objective of the present research work was to develop fast dissolving oral film disintegrating within few second to enhance the convenience of administration to the patient to improve

compliance. Mouth dissolving film also know as an fast dissolving film, quick dissolving Film, rapid dissolving film, oral thin film [OTC] etc. The formulation developed was simple, easy to prepare and economical with great applicability and also giving faster in-vitro drug dissolution rate as compare to tablet. Oral dissolving film should have ability to promote through oral mucosal

layer. Fast dissolving film are preferred in hydrophilic in nature [41,62]

Oral thin film are less sensitive to environmental condition like temperature and humidity. Oral thin film provides excellent mouth feel produced by use of flavour and sweeteners . Various hydrophilic polymers which provide rapid dissolution acceptable mechanical properties and

good mouth feel quality are used a film forming agent.[63]

Water soluble polymer are used film formers as they provide rapid disintegration , good mouth feel , and mechanical strength to the films. Variety of polymers are used for preparation of film like gelatin , xanthum gum , hydroxyl propyl methyl cellulose , modified starch , hydroxyl ethyl cellulose etc.[35,45]

Fig-1: oral fast dissolving film

Special feature of mouth dissolving film

- 1-mouth dissolving film are thin and elongated .
- 2-it show a fast disintegration within 1 minute .
- 3-films are available in various size and shape.
- 4-oral film are excellent mucoadhesion.
- 5-fast disintegration and rapid release [3,4,5]

Ideal characteristics of suitable drug candidate

- 1-the drug have pleasant taste.
- 2-the drug with smaller and moderate molecular weight are preferable.
- 3-the drug should have good solubility and stability in water as well as saliva .
- 4-it should be partially ionized at the PH of oral cavity .
- 5-it should have ability to permeate oral mucosal tissue [6,7,8]

Advantage

- 1- No need of water swallow
- 2- Available in various size and shape
- 3-Hydrate and dissolve oral cavity within a fraction of second

4-Fast disintegration and dissolution

- 5-Taste masking
- 6-Improved patient compliance
- 7-Improved oral absorption and bioavailability
- 8-Rapid onset of action
- 9- Enhanced stability
- 10 - Minimised first pass metabolism [8,9]

Disadvantage

- 1-It is hygroscopic in nature so it must kept in dry places
- 2-Packing of films require special equipment and it difficult to packing
- 3-Need special packing has they must be protected in to oral film
- 4-Eating and drinking may become restricted
- 5-It takes moisture from atmosphere
- 6-Dose uniformity is a challenge [10,11]

Overview of oral cavity

The oral mucosa is composed of an outermost layer of stratified squamous epithelium. Below this lies a basement membrane, a lamina propria

followed by the submucosa as the innermost layer. The oral mucosa in general is intermediate between that of the epidermis and intestinal mucosa in terms of permeability. It is estimated that the permeability of the buccal mucosa is 4-4000 times greater than that of the skin. There are considerable differences in permeability between different regions of the oral cavity because of the diverse structures and functions of the different oral mucosa.[42,46,47]

Sublingual gland

Salivary gland are present in the floor of the mouth underneath the tongue. Sublingual gland are also know as the salivary gland that are located beneath the tongue secrete saliva which get mixed with food , so get food gets lubricated , formed in to a soft bogus and can be easily swallowed. Absorption of the drug is directly from the site in to systemic circulation owing to its relatively

lesser thickness, high permeability and rich blood supply the are also known as sublingual gland. They produce mucin in turn produce saliva.oral cavity is lined with mucous membrane which comprises of squamous cell and mucus gland. Salivary gland contain the group of cell which secrete saliva in to the mouth through salivary duct. Salivary gland includes comprise of parotid , submandibular and sub maxillary glands . The fluid which is produced by the gland get mix with food , so the food gets easily chewed , so it can be said the absorption is directly proportional to layer thickness .[23,64]

The absorption of drug follow in this way sublingual > buccal > gingival > palatal . Due to high permeability and rich blood supply , the sublingual route can produce rapid onset of action so the drug with can short delivery period can be delivered.

Fig : 2 - overview of oral mucosa

Mechanism of absorption

Sublingual administration drug solutes are rapidly absorbed into the reticulated vein, which lies underneath the oral mucosa and transported through the facial veins, internal jugular vein, and braciocephalic vein and are then drained into the systemic circulation. Upon sublingual administration drug reaches directly in to the blood

stream through the ventral surface of the tongue and floor of the mouth.

The main mechanism for the absorption of the drug in to oral mucosa is via passive diffusion into the lipoidal membrane .The absorption of the drug through the sublingual route is 3 to 10 times greater than oral route and is only surpassed by hypodermic injection.[15]

Classification of fast dissolving film and there property

property / sub /type	Flash release water	Mucoadhesive melt-away wafer	Mucoadhesive sustained release wafer
Area [cm ²]	2-8	2-7	2-4
Thickness [μ m]	20-70	50-500	50-250
Structure	Film: single layer	Single or multilayer system	Multi layer system
Excipient	Soluble,highly hydrophilic polymer	Soluble, hydrophilic polymer	Low/non soluble polymer
Application	Tongue [upper plate]	Gingival or buccal region	Gingival,[other region in the oral cavity]
Dissolution	Maximum 60 sec	Disintegration in a few mins, forming gel	Maximum 8-10 hrs
Site of action	Systemic or local	Systemic or local	Systemic or local

[16,17]

Classification of the fast dissolving technology

Fast dissolving technology can be divided in to three group [3,18]

1: Lyophilised system

The technology behind these systems entails forming tablet-shaped units from a drug suspension or solution with other structural excipients using a mould or blister pack. In the pack or mould, the units or tablets are frozen and lyophilised. The resulting units are extremely porous, allowing for rapid water or saliva penetration and disintegration.

2: Compressed tablet- based system

This system is made using standard tablet technology and excipients that are compressed directly. Tablet technologies vary in hardness and friability depending on the manufacturing method. When compared to a standard tablet, the speed of disintegration for fast dissolve tablets is achieved by formulating with either water soluble excipients

super disintegrant or effervescent components, allowing rapid penetration of water into the core of the tablet

3: Thin film strip

Oral films, also known as oral wafers, evolved from the confection and oral care markets in the form of breath strips over the last few years and became a novel and widely accepted form by consumers for delivering vitamins and personal care products. FDFs are now a proven and accepted technology for the systemic delivery of APIs in over-the-counter (OTC) medications, and they are in the early to mid- development stages for prescription drugs.

This has been attributed to the consumer success of breath freshener products like Listerine Pocket Paks in the US consumer market. To create a 50-200 mm film, such systems employ a variety of hydrophilic polymers. The film is made in large sheets and then cut into individual dosages units

for packaging in a pharmaceutically acceptable format.

Comparison between oral film and oral disintegrating tablet

Fast dissolving film	Fast dissolving tablet
Grater dissolution due to large surface	Lesser dissolution due to less surface area
More patient compliance	Less patient compliance than film
Low dose can be incorporated	High dose can be incorporated
No risk of choking	Fear of choking
Better durable than oral disintegrating tablet	Less durable as compared to films

[18,19,20]

Formulation of fast dissolving film

Fast dissolving oral film includes various ingredient for its formulation such as as :

- Active pharmaceutical ingredient
- Film forming polymers
- Plasticiser
- Super disintegrates
- Sweetening agent
- Saliva stimulating agent
- Surfactants
- Flavouring agent
- Colouring agent

Stabilising and thickening agent

Formulation of FDFs involves the intricate application of aesthetic and performance characteristics such as taste masking, fast dissolution, physical appearance, mouth feel etc. From the regulatory perspectives, all excipients used in the formulation of OS should be Generally Regarded as Safe (i.e. GRAS-listed) and should be approved for use in oral pharmaceutical dosage forms. A typical composition includes various ingredients which are described in the Table

A typical composition contain the following ingredients.

Agent	Concentration
Drug	1-25%
Water soluble polymer	40-50%
Plasticizer	0-20%
Fillers, colours, flavours etc	0-40%

Active pharmaceutical ingredients

The film composition contains 1-30% w/w of the active pharmaceutical ingredient. Always use low dose active pharmaceutical ingredients because high dose of drug are difficult to incorporate in fast

dissolving film. A number of drugs can be used as fast dissolving oral film including anti-histamine, anti- diarrheal, anti-depressants, vasodilators, anti-asthmatic, antiemetic, mouth ulcer etc. [24,56]

Drug	Dose	Therapeutic action
Nicotine	2mg	Smoking cessation
Diphenhydramine HCL	25mg	Anti allergic

Ondansetran	2.5mg	Anti emetic
Cetirizine	5-10mg	Anti allergic
Ketoprofen	12.5mg	Analgesic
Omeprazole	10-20mg	Proton pump inhibitor
Salbutamol	4mg	Anti histamines

Film forming polymer

Polymer is the major and most essential component of FDOFs. A variety of polymers are available for preparation of oral film and these are used in the concentration of about 40-45% w/w of total film weight but can be increased up to 65%w/w of film weight alone or in combination to obtain desired properties of oral film.

The film obtained should be tough enough so that there may not be any damage while handling or during transportation. The robustness of the film depends on the type of polymer and the amount in the formulation. The polymer used should be non-toxic non-irritant and good wetting and spreading properties. The polymer should be reasonable price and widely available.[25,26,54,55]

Natural polymer	Synthetic polymer
Pullulan	Hydroxy propyl methyl cellulose
Starch	Polyvinyl alcohol
Pectine	Carboxy methyl cellulose
Xanthan	Hydroxy ethyl cellulose
Gelatin	Poly vinyl pyrrolidone
Gum acacia	Poly ethylene oxidase
Sodium alginate	Methyl cellulose

Plasticisers

Plasticiser is an essential component of the oral film formulation. It aids in the improvement of the strip's flexibility and decreases its brittleness. Plasticisers play an important role in improving strip properties by lowering the polymer's glass transition temperature. The plasticiser chosen will be determined by its compatibility with the polymer as well as the type of solvent used in film casting. The use of plasticiser improves the flow of

polymer and increases the polymer's strength. Plasticisers that are commonly used include glycerol, propylene glycol, di-butylphthalate, and polyethylene glycols, among others. Incorrect plasticiser use can cause film splitting or cracking. The use of certain plasticisers may affect the rate of drug absorption. The permanent should be imparted to the strip by the plasticiser used. Plasticisers should be compatible with the drug as well as other excipients used in strip

preparation. With hydroxyl-containing plasticisers such as PEG, propylene glycol, glycerol, and polyols, cellulosic hydrophilic polymers were easily plasticised. Glycerol is a better polyvinyl alcohol plasticiser than diethylene glycol, which can be used for both hypromellose and polyvinyl alcohol films [27,57]

Saliva stimulating agent

The use of saliva stimulating agents is intended to increase the rate of saliva production, which will aid in the faster disintegration of the rapid dissolving strip formulations. In general, acids used in food preparation, such as citric acid, Malic acid, lactic acid, ascorbic acid, and tartaric acid, can be used as salivary stimulants. These agents are used alone or in combinations ranging from 2 to 6%w/w of the strip's weight.[28]

Sweetening agent

Sweeteners have evolved into an essential component of formulations designed to be disintegrated or dissolved in the oral cavity. Natural and artificial sweeteners are both used in the formulation of fast dissolving films. Sweeteners are typically used in formulations at concentrations ranging from 3-6%w/w, either alone or in combination. Polyhydric alcohols such as sorbitol, mannitol, and isomalt can be combined to provide a good mouth-feel and cooling sensation. The classical source of the sweetener is sucrose, fructose, glucose, liquid glucose and isomaltose. The sweetness of fructose is perceived rapidly in the mouth as compared to sucrose and dextrose.[29,30,59]

Sweetening agent	Example
Natural sweeteners	Xylose, ribose, glucose, galactose, fructose, Dextrose, sucrose, maltose
Artificial sweeteners	First generation- saccharine, cyclamate, and Aspartame Second generation- acesulfame, sucralose, alitame

Surfactant

Surfactants are used as a solubilising, wetting, or dispersing agent, allowing the film to dissolve in seconds and release the active agent immediately. Sodium lauryl sulphate, benzalkonium chloride, benzethonium chloride, tweens, and other commonly used ingredients. One of the most important surfactants is poloxamer 407, which is used as a solubiliser, wetting agent, and dispersant [6,58]

Flavouring agent

OFDF formulations should contain up to 10%w/w flavours. An individual's acceptance of an oral disintegrating or dissolving formulation is largely determined by the initial flavour quality observed in the first few seconds after the product has been

consumed, as well as the after taste of the formulation, which lasts for at least 10 minutes. The flavour chosen is determined by the type of drug to be included in the formulation. It was discovered that age has a significant impact on taste fondness. The elderly prefers mint or orange flavours, whereas the younger generation prefer fruit punch, raspberry, and so on. Flavouring agents can be chosen from a variety of synthetic flavour oils, oleo resins, and extracts derived from various parts of the plant. Plants with leaves, fruits, and flowers. Flavours can be used alone or in combination. Flavour oils include peppermint oil, cinnamon oil, spearmint oil, and nutmeg oil, whereas fruity flavours include vanilla, cocoa, coffee, chocolate, and citrus. Fruit essences

include apple, raspberry, cherry, and pineapple, to name a few.[31,32,60]

Flavouring agent	Example
Flavour oil	Peppermint oil, cinnamon oil, spearmint oil
Fruity flavour	Coffee, cocoa, citrus, vanilla, chocolate

Colouring agent

There is a wide variety of colours available, including FD&C colours, EU colours, Natural colours, and custom Pantone-matched colours. Some saliva stimulating agents may be added to improve disintegration and speed up release. Citric acid, tartaric acid, malic acid, ascorbic acid, and succinic acid are some of these agents. [33,34]

Stabilising and thickening agents

The stabilising and thickening agents are employed to improve the viscosity and consistency of dispersion or solution of the strip preparation solution or suspension before casting. Natural gums like xanthan gum, locust bean gum, carragenan and cellulosic derivatives can be used in the concentration up to 5%w/w as thickening agents and stabilising agents.[45]

Manufacturing method

- 1: Solvent costing method
- 2: Semi solid casting method
- 3: Hot melt extrusion method
- 4: Solid dispersion extrusion method
- 5: Rolling method

Solvent casting method

Fast dissolving buccal films are preferably formulated using the solvent casting method, whereby the water soluble ingredients are dissolved to form a clear viscous solution and the drug along with other excipients is dissolved in suitable solvent then both the solutions are mixed and stirred and finally casted in to the Petri plate and dried.[35,61]

Semi solid casting method method

In this method, a solution of water-soluble film forming polymer is prepared and added to a solution of acid insoluble polymer (e.g., cellulose acetate phthalate, cellulose acetate butyrate) prepared in ammonium or sodium hydroxide. The appropriate amount of plasticiser should then be added to form a gel mass. Finally, using heat-controlled drums, the gel mass should be cast into the films or ribbons. The thickness of the formed film will be between 0.015 and 0.05 inches. In this method, the acid insoluble polymer to film forming polymer ratio must be 1:4.[36,44]

Hot melt extrusion

In the hot melt extrusion method, as shown in Fig.9, the initial mass must be dried and obtained with carriers as the drug is mixed with carriers and obtained as solid mass, then the mass is introduced into an extruder divided into four zones with varying degrees of temperature, zone 1 at 800°C, zone 2 at 150°C, zone 3 at 1000°C, and zone 4 at 650°C. To process the granules inside the barrel of the extruder for 3-4 minutes, set the extruder speed

to 15 rpm. After being pressed into a cylindrical calendar, the film is obtained. Hot melt extrusion has many advantages, such as limited operation units. It reduces waste and eliminates the need for the Because of intense mixing and agitation, the use of solvent or water (anhydrous) results in uniform content.[37,53]

Solid dispersion extrusion

Immiscible components are extruded with drug in this method, and then solid dispersions are

prepared. Finally, dies are used to shape the solid dispersions into films.[41,52]

Rolling method

A drug-containing solution or suspension is rolled on a carrier in the rolling method. The solvent is mostly water or a water-alcohol mixture. The film is dried on the rollers before being cut into the desired shapes and sizes. Using a high shear processor, other ingredients, including the active agent, are dissolved in a small amount of aqueous solvent. Hydrocolloids that dissolve in water to form a homogeneous viscous solution.[38,51]

Evaluation of fast dissolving oral film

[11,14,39,40,48,49,50]

1: Thickness test

The thickness of strip can be measured by micrometer screw gauge at different strategic locations. This is essential to ascertain uniformity in the thickness of the film as this is directly related to the accuracy of dose in the strip.

2: Organoleptic evaluation

For evaluation of the product, special controlled human taste panels are used. In-vitro methods of utilizing taste sensors, are being used for this purpose. These in-vitro taste assessment apparatus and methodologies are well suited for high-throughout taste screening of oral film.

3: Dryness test

Tack is the tenacity with which the strip adheres to an accessory (a piece of paper) that has been pressed into contact with the strip

4: Tensile strength

Tensile strength is the maximum stress applied to a point at which the strip specimen breaks. It is calculated by the applied load at rupture divided by the cross-sectional area of the strip as given in the equation below:

5: Tear resistance

Tear resistance of plastic film or sheeting is a complex function of its ultimate resistance to rupture. Basically very low rate of loading 51 mm (2 in)/min is employed to measure the force to initiate tearing. The maximum stress or force (that is generally found near the onset of tearing) required to tear the specimen is recorded as the tear resistance value in Newtons

6: Folding endurance

Folding endurance is determined by repeated folding of the strip at the same place till the strip breaks. The number of times the film is folded without breaking is computed as the folding endurance value.

7: Swelling property

Film swelling study is conducted using simulated saliva solution. Each film sample is weighed and placed in a preweighed stainless steel wire mesh. The mesh containing film sample is submerged into 15ml medium in a plastic container. Increase in the weight of the film is determined at preset time interval until a constant weight is observed.

The degree of swelling is calculated using formula-

$$\alpha = (wt - w_0)/w_0$$

wt is weight of film at time

t, and w_0 is weight of film at time zero.

8: Contact angle

Contact angle measurements are performed at the room temperature with a goniometry. A drop of double distilled water was placed on the surface of the dry film. Images of the water droplet were recorded by means of digital camera, digital images are analysed by the image 1.28v software for angle determination

9: Disintegration time

The disintegration time limit of 30 s or less for orally disintegrating tablets described in CDER guidance can be applied to fast dissolving oral strips [44]. Although, no official guidance is available for oral fast disintegrating films/strips, this may be used as a qualitative guideline for quality control test or at development stage. Pharmacopoeial disintegrating test apparatus may be used for this study. Typical disintegration time for strips is 5–30 s.

10: Weight variation

3 × 2 cm film was cut at three different places in the cast film. The weight of each film strip was taken and then weight variation observed.

11: Surface PH measurement

The surface pH of Mouth dissolving film is determined in order to investigate the possibility of any side effects in vivo. As an acidic or alkaline pH may cause irritation to the oral mucosa, it is determined to keep the surface pH as close to neutral as possible.

CONCLUSION

The study successfully demonstrated that oral fast-dissolving film are an effective and patient-

friendly drug delivery system. The formulated films showed satisfactory mechanical strength, uniform drug distribution, rapid disintegration, and acceptable physiochemical stability. The quick dissolution in the oral cavity without the need of water makes them particularly suitable for paediatric, geriatric As well as for situation requiring rapid onset of therapeutic action. Overall, the result indicate the oral fast-dissolving films offers a promising alternative to conventional dosage forms and have strong potential for further development and clinical application. Oral fast-dissolving films represent a rapidly advancing area of drug delivery technology and their future holds significant potential for innovation and clinical use. In the coming years, oral fast-dissolving film are likely expand conventional small-molecule drugs to include peptides, probiotic and personalised medicines. On going research is expected to focus improving strength, taste masking, stability and drug loading capacity. Benefits of oral fast-dissolving films rapid onset of action, no need of water, improving patient compliance, enhanced bioavailability, accurate dosing, reduce risk of choking etc.

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